

Report on Newcastle Disease in Peafowls and Brahma Chicken

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Bacterial culture and identification from cloacal swab samples and hemagglutination inhibition test (HI) from serum samples of 4 peacocks exhibiting clinical signs of Newcastle disease are described together with postmortem findings in brahma cock raised with the peacocks in a royal house in Sokoto, Nigeria. The Brahma cock died suddenly without showing sign of disease. Bacterial culture revealed the growth of *Escherichia coli* and HI titer was 6 and 7 from two of the Peafowls indicating high antibody titers. Post mortem on the Brahma cock showed legions suggestive of Newcastle disease caused by velogenic strain of the virus. This is the first report on ND in Peafowls in Sokoto Nigeria. It is believed that the Peafowls and the chicken were infected as a result of improper biosecurity and waiting too long (over three months) before revaccination against ND. The antibody titre might have waned subjecting them to natural infection. The owners were advised to ensure strict preventive measures against future occurrence and it is recommended that further research should be conducted to isolate and characterize the virus in Peafowls in this area.

Key words: Brahma chickens, Newcastle disease, outbreak, peafowls, royal house.

INTRODUCTION

Peafowl are considered to be exotic birds in many parts of the world. They are native to India, Java, Assam, Burma, Siam, Ceylon and Malaya and were first brought from India to Syria and Egypt about 3,000 years ago by Phoenicians (Yenilmez, 2020). Peafowl known with its spectacular feather colors are commonly kept in the households of the wealthy and royals in Northern parts of Nigeria for display. Apart from the peafowl, other birds usually kept for the same ornamental purpose are parrots and some breeds of chickens like the Brahma and Silky, horses are also kept by these people of high societal status, all the mentioned animals serve as symbols of wealth and power. The males of peafowl known as the peacocks have crested heads, long legs, and brilliant tail feathers called the train feathers which can be erected

and fanned out, they have iridescent spots called the eyes in adults. For this reason, the peacocks are more recognized than the peahens (Kane *et al.*, 2018). Peacocks are the largest flying birds among all the birds. The peafowl can be produced in many parts of the world because they have a strong structure and adaptability (Yenilmez, 2020). The peafowl has 15 known colors: Blue, green, white, purple, cameo, charcoal, opal, bronze, peach, midnight, jade, taupe, sonja's violeta, hazel and indigo (Kane *et al.*, 2018). Tourists and visitors, whom traditionally visit ancient and royal places are usually attracted by these magnificent birds, observe their behavior and habitat and even participate in feeding them (Lawal, 2024).

The Giant Brahma chickens have gained immense popularity among backyard chicken enthusiasts for their large body size, charming color variety and friendly nature and the charming variety. They are sociable backyard chickens renowned for their calm and docile

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temperament. With their fluffy feathering and stout build, Brahma chickens can endure chilly harmattan more than many other breeds (Anon, 2023).

Newcastle disease (ND) is a highly contagious viral disease of domestic poultry, cage and aviary birds, and wild birds. It is mostly seen in domestic with a rapidly fatal and high-mortality rate characterized by gastrointestinal, respiratory and/or nervous signs. In other avian species, the disease produced by virulent ND viruses ranges clinically from inapparent to a rapidly fatal condition (Broomand *et al.*, 2015). Newcastle disease (ND) is still a threat to the poultry industry in Sokoto in spite of routine vaccination of commercial and occasionally backyard poultry with both live and killed vaccines. This is not unconnected with contact with carrier birds regarded as susceptible populations which include backyard chicken, ducks, and turkeys, pet and wild birds. These birds are not usually vaccinated and are highly susceptible to Newcastle disease virus (NDV) infections (Vijayarani *et al.*, 2010). Newcastle disease virus has a very wide host range. The severity of ND depends on the pathotype of the virus infecting the birds and the species of bird infected (Kaleta and Baldauf, 1988).

As there are few reports on ND in Peafowls worldwide, this is a report on Newcastle disease outbreak in Peacocks and Brahma chickens kept for ornamental purpose in a royal house in Sokoto.

CASE REPORT

Case history

On 18th September, 2024 there was request from one of the royal houses in Sokoto, Nigeria for ambulatory visit by the Veterinary Teaching Hospital to examine their birds which were showing signs of disease and dying, there was also complaint of inappetence. On visiting the house, the birds were found to include two breeds of Peafowls of different ages, three brahma chickens and an adult male parrot. The peafowls were thirty two (32) in number, two (2) adult female pure white breed which were initially four (4) but the 2 males died leaving only the females, There were also seven (7) adult blue/green ones, 3 males and 4 females which were initially ten (10) but three (3) died earlier. Others were 11 growers (between 2 weeks and 24 weeks of age) and twelve (12) chicks all blue/green breed, about 13 of them died earlier as well. They were fed with commercial grower feed together with the chicken (2 hens and one cock). The parrot was caged and fed with peanuts. The adult peafowls move freely around the house premises. The peachicks that were below two weeks of age were kept in cages with their mothers. They were usually vaccinated with Lasota vaccine at eight weeks interval, routinely dewormed and given multivitamin occasionally. From record, last vaccination was done twelve (12) weeks

before the current disease report.

Clinical manifestation and diagnosis

Some of the peacocks appeared apparently healthy while others (four adults,) were isolated, weak, dull and reluctant to move. Among them, two passed greenish-white watery diarrhea, had ruffled feathers with dropped wings and one manifested torticollis (Figures 1-4). A dead one was met which was reported to have died in the night before the report.

Figure 1: Dropped wings in a peacock

Figure 2: Greenish white diarrhea and ruffled feathers

Figure 3

Figures 3 and 4: Peafowls in isolation, showing dullness and also manifested torticollis

Figure 5: Dead white peacock

Cloacal swabs were taken using sterile swab stick for bacterial culture and antibiotic susceptibility testing (AST) and blood samples were taken for sera extraction and serology. Blood samples were collected through the brachial vein from two peacocks that exhibited torticollis and passed diarrhea respectively. The samples were dispensed into 2ml microcentrifuge tubes and transported to the clinical pathology laboratory of VTH for sera extraction.

Management

The four peafowls that showed signs of disease were isolated in a cage within the back yard of the house and all were treated with Enrofloxacin 10% at 25mg/kg BW and KC-vite multivitamin 1ml/10 birds oral solutions were administered for five days.

The following day, the 23-week Brahma cock (Figure 5) was brought dead to the post mortem unit of Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto for post mortem examination (Figure

6). History further revealed that the bird did not show any signs of disease but was seen lifeless a few hours prior to presentation. Post mortem examination was conducted on the carcass.

Figure 7: The Brahma cock few hours after death

Bacterial isolation

Bacterial isolation and identification using the fecal sample was carried out as recommended by Procop *et al* (2020). The sample were streaked onto prepared MacConkey agar plates and then incubated at 37°C for an additional 24 hours. The colonies exhibiting lactose fermentation were subjected to Gram staining, and gram-negative rods observed under a light microscope were carefully chosen for subculturing. Lactose fermenting colonies on MacConkey plate were streaked onto EMB agar plate for presumptive confirmation as *E. coli*. Purplish colonies associated with green metallic sheen was picked and streaked on Nutrient agar slant, incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and stored at 4°C pending further biochemical characterisation of *E. coli*. Isolates from EMB were subcultured for 24 hours on Nutrient agar and subjected to biochemical identification of Indole, Methyl Red, Voges prausker and citrate and interpreted following standard protocol.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was done using the Kirby Bauer disc diffusion test and interpreted. Multiple antibiotics disc (Oxoid, USA) was used according to CLSI (2019) standard.

Serology

The collected blood samples were kept at room temperature and transported to clinical pathology laboratory Faculty of Veterinary Medicine UDUS for sera extraction. The blood was centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 3 minutes to extract sera. Hemagglutination-inhibition test was carried out to determine serum antibody titer against Newcastle disease virus. The HI assay was done using 96 'U'-well micro titer plates, using doubling dilution in PBS (0.01M) at of pH 7.2.using standard procedure as described by Killian (2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bacterial Culture, Isolation and Identification

Colonies exhibited typical *Escherichia coli* characteristics after using biochemical means. The birds probably came into contact with pathogenic strains of the bacteria through contaminated premises and/or aerosol as they are exposed to environmental contaminants and suffered the disease as a of concurrent infection resulting to lowered immunity. Inhalation of contaminated dust is the most common source of infection with *E. coli* in poultry (Nolan *et al.* (2013). Charlton (2006) reported that adverse reactions from routine vaccinations can damage to the respiratory tract leading to pathogenic bacteria

entering blood stream which can lead to septicaemia.

Antibiotic Sensitivity Test Results

The isolates displayed sensitivity to Ciprofloxacin and Gentamicin and resistance to Amoxicillin, Erythromycin and Tetracycline the tested drugs are among the drugs effective in treating Colibacillosis. The antibiotics the organism was resistant to are among the commonly abused antibiotics by farmers in the study area. Mungadi and Abdullahi (2024) reported 70% resistance by *E. coli* isolated from cloacal swabs of different types of chicken in Sokoto to Oxytetracycline. It has been reported by Oluwasile *et al.*, (2014) and Agyare *et al* (2019) that almost all known antibiotics are increasingly losing their activity against pathogenic microorganisms. Also Aworh *et al.* (2020) reported high prevalence (37.8%) of Extended-spectrum β -lactamase producing *E. coli* in chickens in Abuja Nigeria where tetracycline, sulphonamides and aminoglycosides class of antimicrobials accounted for the majority of the resistance determinant. Adebowale *et al.* (2022) multidrug resistant *E. coli* in chickens from live bird markets in Ogun state, Nigeria while Ojo *et al.*, (2012) reported 76.9% *E. coli* resistance to tetracycline in free range chickens in Abeakuta Nigeria.

Hemagglutination inhibition test result

After conducting HI test, the antibody titres were \log_2^6 for Sample1 and \log_2^7 for sample 2. Antibodytitre protective standard for birds against Newcastle disease is \log_2^4 (OIE 2012). In birds that were not vaccinated against NDV for up to 12 weeks, high antibody titre can suggest response to natural infection. Broomand *et al*, (2015) reported Newcastle disease in peafowls in Iran which was confirmed by serology (HI) and PCR with HI antibody titer ranging from 8-12. The titer is close to what was obtained in this report. There was also report of isolation of NDV from peacock in India and China by Vijayarani *et al* (2010) and Dou and Yang (2007) respectively. Mustafa *et al.*, (2015) published first report of NDV in peacocks in Tharparker region of Pakistan by administration of questionnaires to farmers which consisted of record of the disease in peacocks in different parts of the region by manifestation of signs of the disease.

Postmortem result

The carcass was fresh indicating autolysis had not set in. There were dried discharges from the oral cavity and mucoid exudates on the tongue. The trachea was congested, the air sacs were cloudy (air sacculitis) and there were petechial hemorrhages on the proventriculus and Ecchymotic hemorrhages of the ileo-cecal area. These were suggestive of ND as shown in figures 8-11. Intestinal and lungs tissues cultured from the carcass of

Figure 8: Congested trachea

Figure 9: Cloudy air sacs

Figure 10: Petechial hemorrhages on the proventriculus

Figure 11: Ecchymotic hemorrhages of the ileo-cecal area

Figure 12: Culture yielded no bacterial growth

the Brahma cock revealed no bacterial growth (Figure 12).

Post mortem findings by Broomand *et al* (2015) were similar to what was obtained in this studies which included petechial haemorrhages on the mucosal surface of trachea, proventriculus, small intestine and cecal tonsils and air sacculitis. The ND virus isolated by Vijayarani *et al*, (2010) from peacock is a velogenic one and it was interestingly observed that in their study, there was the lack of clinical signs. Nevertheless, the postmortem results indicated the involvement of pathogenic NDV with pneumotropic and viscerotropic lesions just as seen in the Brahma cock in this report

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Even though there have been several reports on ND in both local and commercial chickens, this is the first known report on the disease in peafowls in Sokoto Nigeria. Velogenic strains of the virus are continuously in circulation and can cause acute disease with severe postmortem lesions. It is recommended that further research should be conducted to isolate and characterize the virus in peafowl in this area.

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